

Evaluating the performance of Pixel-based vs. Object-based classifiers for Extracting High Resolution Land cover product from SPOT 6 imagery

Mahlatse Kganyago^{1*}, Phila Sibandze¹

¹ South African National Space Agency (SANSA), Earth Observation Directorate, Mark Shuttleworth Street, The Enterprise Building, Pretoria, 0001.

*mkganyago@sansa.org.za

Abstract

Remote sensing measurements provide an accurate and timeous record of the landscape components. This enables the extraction of important information from images pertaining to spatial distribution of land cover captured by various earth observation satellites. Hence, up-to-date land cover information is of critical importance to planners, scientists, resource managers, decision makers and various applications. The choice of an optimum sensor for land cover mapping is influenced by its spatial, temporal resolution and spectral resolution. Therefore the availability of new earth observation data, such as SPOT 6, which has improved spatial and spectral resolutions from its predecessor, revolutionize the utility of contemporary methods for land cover mapping. Recognizing the opportunity to map land cover at high resolution from SPOT 6, this evaluated the conventional pixel-based classification methods (namely; supervised Maximum Likelihood Classifier and unsupervised ISODATA classifier) and object-based (K-Nearest Neighbour) classification methods for their performance in mapping land cover in a semi-arid environment. Semi-arid environments are usually comprised of discrete land cover units, as a result, sophisticate land cover mapping activities since the resultant classes are largely generalised especially when using high spatial resolution data. This was identified as a gap; and therefore, was addressed. The study found that object-based K-NN classifier performed better than pixel-based ISODATA and Maximum Likelihood classifiers, with overall accuracies of 82%, 50.7% and 36.7% respectively. We concluded that SPOT 6 data, coupled with object-based classification methods have potential to provide rapid land cover classifications for South Africa.

1. Introduction

Remote Sensing has the capability to provide detailed, quantitative characteristics of the land surface information at various spatial and temporal resolutions. It also provides greater amount of information on geographic distribution of different land cover types and has the advantages of making available, large archived data that can be used to identify trends in resource conditions, saving time and cost as compared with other conventional inventories and surveys (Prenzel 2004; Yuan et al., 2005; Kim and Daigle 2011). Land cover refers to the suite of natural and man-made features that blankets the earth's surface (Wessels et al., 2004). Updated land cover information provides a synoptic view of the landscape's characteristics and enables decision making on interrelated aspects of most activities on the land surface (Memarian et al., 2013). As a result, it is

fundamental in different applications such as land use mapping, vegetation monitoring, land-cover change analysis, hydrological modelling, site suitability analysis, urban planning and other earth science applications.

Land cover classification for global and regional studies has been successful in the past using coarse resolution data such as Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectrometer (MODIS), Advanced Very High Resolution Radiometer (AVHRR) and Medium Resolution Imaging Spectrometer (MERIS). Loveland et al. (2000) developed a global land cover database, useful for global environmental modelling and assessment using 1 km resolution AVHRR. While, Wessels et al. (2004) applied a much finer resolution of 250 and 500 meters spatial resolution of MODIS data for mapping land cover characteristics in the USA and Brazil. Both studies concluded that MODIS data was suitable for mapping extensive land cover types such as regional forest and non-forest areas. Similarly, Clevers et al. (2005) used full resolution MERIS data at 300m for mapping land cover at Netherlands and found moderate accuracy when classifying major land cover types. The literature reviewed indicated that low spatial resolution land cover products are useful for providing rapid regional land cover and for mapping the extreme human impact such as deforestation (Wessels et al., 2004), while, high spatial resolution products are suitable for detailed monitoring and mapping.

Medium resolution sensors of 10m to 30m from Landsat TM, Landsat ETM+, SPOT 5 and ASTER have been used in previous studies to map land cover in Saudi Arabia, Iran and Malaysia (Matinfar et al. 2007, Al-Ahmadi and Hames 2009, Memarian et al. 2013). South Africa conducted the first land cover study in 1994 which was at a national scale. Subsequent to that, another national study was conducted in 2000 (SANBI 2009). Both studies used archived Landsat data between 1994 and 2000. The National Land Cover (NLC) produced in 2000 has since been updated using independently generated provincial datasets from SPOT 5 imagery of 2005 to 2009 (ARC 2010). However, the spatial resolution of the NLC is not suitable for localized municipal studies due to its coarse resolution. There is a high demand for improved land cover data sets on a national scale. Aerial photography offers high resolution dataset, however producing landcover at a national scale can be a challenging and colossal task. Therefore, satellite data with comparable properties is often preferred as it is less costly, easily accessible and has greater ground coverage.

The advent of highly improved spatial and spectral resolution satellite-based sensors, such as IKONOS, QUICKBIRD, WorldView-2 and SPOT 6 substitutes the need for extensive acquisition of aerial surveys and poses new challenges in land cover mapping. Traditional pixel-based image classification methods are inefficient in taking full advantage of the level of detail available in new high resolution data (Barbosa and Maillard 2010). Each object in high resolution data represents characteristics of multiple pixels (i.e. objects are larger than pixel size) resulting in increased intra-class spectral variability (Hu et al. 2013). Hence, statistical separability between classes which is crucial for most pixel-based methods is reduced. Also, Complex, semi-arid environments

complicates classifications processes, hence considerably affect the accuracy. There is a need for continuous evaluation of the performance of current classifiers on new high resolution data and in complex environments, to facilitate accurate land cover mapping. Barbosa and Maillard (2010) assessed the potential of a new region-based classifier to map land cover in a complex wetland environment. They found that unsupervised region-based classification had superior spatial consistency and allowed easier visual interpretation of the classified image when compared to conventional supervised (Maximum Likelihood) and unsupervised (ISODATA) algorithm. Oruc et al. (2004) found that unsupervised classification using ISODATA algorithm and supervised classification using parallelepiped, minimum-distance and maximum-likelihood resulted in lower classification accuracies (66.86%) when compared to object-based image classification (81.3%) in forested and mining environment. Similarly, Whiteside and Ahmad (2005) found that the overall accuracy for object-oriented classification was 78%, whilst for pixel-based classification was 69.1%.

The launch of SPOT 6 satellite in September, 2013 provides an opportunity to generate a NLC dataset for South Africa, at relatively reduced cost and at frequent intervals to allow detection of rapid changes in land cover. SPOT 6 data has four multispectral bands in blue, green, red and near infrared regions, acquired at a spatial resolution of 6 metres and a panchromatic band of 1.5 metres. This study present two aspects, the first one is an evaluation of pixel-based and object-based classification methods for their performance on SPOT 6 data, and the last one being, the demonstration of SPOT 6 data for providing high resolution land cover product. Pixel-based classifiers identify each image pixel as an independent observation, regardless of its spatial context (Marcal 2005). While on the other hand, object-based classifiers consider the object's shape, size, texture, spectral properties and context of objects, resulting to more comprehensive results. Of interest is that, object-based classification methods are increasingly becoming the preferred method to use than pixel-based classification for land cover mapping activities. The hypothesis tested in this study was that, object-based classification has higher accuracy than the conventional pixel-based supervised and unsupervised classifications. This study will provide new insights in the application of automated object-based classification for arid and semi-arid areas.

2. Study Area

Musina is the northern most town of South Africa, situated about 8km from the Limpopo River which separate South Africa and Zimbabwe. The area receives summer rainfall, as a result the Sand River which is a tributary of the Limpopo River flows during this period. Musina is location at 22°20'17"S and 30°02'30"E (Figure 1) and is dominated by semi-arid with high temperatures all year-round. There is about 372mm average summer rain with extremely dry winters. As a result the vegetation is largely dominated by low-shrubs and dispersed thorny trees.

Figure 1: Musina in Limpopo province, South Africa

3. Materials and Methods

The SPOT 6 data acquired on the 13th of October 2013 used in the project was supplied by the South African National Space Agency (SANSA). The data had 4 bands in the visible and near infrared (VNIR) regions and one panchromatic band with spatial resolution of 6m and 1.5m respectively. In addition, SANSA also provided the aerial photographs captured in 2009 with a spatial resolution of 0.5 meters. The data (SPOT 6) was pan sharpened to 1.5m to obtain a higher resolution land cover product as recommended by Alparone et al. (2007). The pan-sharpening algorithm in PCI Geomatica improved the spatial resolution while maintaining the spectral information of the data. This process ensured that the derived products contain spectral information for further processing (i.e. classification) and improved the spatial resolution for convenient interpretation. Additionally, a series of six aerial photographs covering the entire study area, were mosaicked. The mosaicking process overlaid geo-referenced multi-resolution photographs while preserving their geometric location, removed the cut-lines and applied colour balancing so that the overlaid photographs may have the same statistical range. The mosaic was clipped to the spatial extent of SPOT 6 data and used as reference data.

Object-based classification requires that images be partitioned into meaningful object, representing the groups of pixels that are relatively homogenous, both spectrally and texturally, and are semantically significant (Blaschke 2010). Oruc et al. (2004) deemed this process an important and primary phase in object-based classification, since they form the basis for subsequent image processing. The Multi resolution algorithm used is a robust and repeatable procedure that has been proven to be successful for various applications (Budreski et al. 2007). This technique considers the spectral and shape information of the image objects to perform segmentation across the entire image. A top-down Multi resolution segmentation algorithm, with a scale parameter of 30 and

default homogeneity criteria (i.e. shape and compactness) was applied to all pan-sharpened image bands. The image layers were weighted the same, so that all spectral information contained in different bands can be considered in the segmentation process. The decision for the applied scale parameter was based on iterative procedure (attempting different scale parameters) to search for segments which represents the image objects as much as possible.

3.1 Land cover classification

The classes were defined based on the guidelines suggested by Congalton (1991) and the classification scheme published by the Chief Directorate National Geospatial Information (CD: NGI). The user defined classes for this study are: bare land, built-up areas, grassland, mining, tarred roads, water, sparse vegetation and dense vegetation.

3.1.1. Pixel-based classification

The Iterative Self-Organising Data Analysis (ISODATA) and Maximum Likelihood algorithms were considered for pixel-based classifications based on their previous successful application (Odindi *et al.* 2012). The ISODATA method is a flexible and adaptable algorithm that assumes that each class has multivariate normal distribution and requires the class means and covariance matrices for each class. It enables the user to determine the minimum and maximum number of clusters, standard deviation and number of iterations, among other parameters. The detailed mathematical expression for ISODATA is illustrated in Ahmad and Sufahani (2012). There were 8 to 16 clusters which were determined for this study, representing the minimum and maximum number of clusters respectively. To acquire the required classes, 10 iterations and 0.95 convergence thresholds were used whilst Euclidian distance default of 4.00 was retained.

For the Maximum Likelihood (ML) classifier which is a supervised classification algorithm used the training data as a way of estimating means and variances of the classes, which are then used to estimate the probabilities (Cambell and Wynne 2011) that a pixel belongs to a particular class based on a posterior probability of membership and dimensions equal to a number of bands in the original image (Memarian *et al.* 2013). The training pixels for all classes were carefully selected to represent the most spectral characteristics of the each class across the entire image (Table 1). These were then used to compute class-to-class separability using Jeffries-Matusita distance to determine the degree to which the spectral characteristics of each class to the other are similar or different and to explain possible misclassifications due to spectral confusion.

Table 1: Distribution of training pixels

Class	No. of pixels	Area (Ha)
Bare land	27,525	6.193
Built-up areas	71,847	16.166
Grassland	23,091	5.195
Mining	11,243	2.530
Tarred Roads	5,007	1.127
Water	5,335	1.200
Sparse Vegetation	28,964	6.517
Dense Vegetation	9,595	2.159

3.1.2. Object-based classification

An object-based K-Nearest Neighbour (*K*-NN) classifier was applied to the results of segmentation. *K*-NN is a non-parametric, machine learning algorithm which classifies the objects according to the Euclidian distance from their neighbours. The parameter ‘*K*’ denotes the number of neighbours in the *n*-dimensional space (where *n* is the number of object attributes) which are considered for classification. The optimal *K* is dependent on the dataset and training data (Memarian et al. 2012). If *K*=1, the object is classified as the class of the object nearest to it. Although the use of the same training areas as in Maximum Likelihood classifier was desired for *K*-NN, however this was not possible since the basis of the two methods different, that is, one was based on pixels the other on objects. Several objects representing spectral, spatial, textural and shape properties of eight target land cover classes were selected across the entire image using the spectral, textural, and spatial information contained in all bands and were saved in memory. *K* value of 5 was considered optimal for the dataset, after experimenting with several other values. Subsequently, *K*-NN classifier was applied on the image object level domain.

3.1.3. Accuracy assessment

A simple random sampling method was used to collect 300 validation points across the aerial photographs covering the study area. These were labelled according to the classes similar to the classification and used as a surrogate for ground observation. A confusion matrix for ISODATA, ML and *K*-NN classifications was computed using the same ground truth sample and producers and the user’s accuracies were calculated for each classifier. A KHAT statistic was calculated from Cohen’s Kappa analysis for each matrix (Formula 1) with values above 0.80 representing strong agreement between the classified map and ground truth and values below 0.40 representing poor agreement (Congalton 1991).

$$\hat{K} = \frac{N \sum_{i=1}^r x_{ii} - \sum_{i=1}^r (x_{i+*} + x_{*i})}{N^2 - \sum_{i=1}^r (x_{i+*} + x_{*i})} \quad [1]$$

Where: \hat{K} = is the KHAT statistic

x_{ii} is the number of diagonal entries in row *i* and column *i*

x_{i+} is the sum of row i
 x_{+i} is the sum of column i
 N is the total number of observations
 r is the size of the matrix

4. Results and Discussions

4.1 Pixel-based classifications

ISODATA classifier yielded 16 classes which represented spectral differences in the data. These were labeled and merged based on visual interpretation of the original SPOT 6 image to form the target land cover classes. The final ISODATA map consisted of six classes, namely; bare land, sparse vegetation, dense vegetation, Built-up areas, Water bodies and grassland (Figure 2). Figure 2 indicates that ISODATA classifier was unable to detect the spectral properties of tarred roads and mining; hence these were misclassified to other classes' mainly built-up areas. This was consistent with the findings of Ahmad and Sufahani (2012) where ISODATA was unable to detect three classes due to statistical similarity.

Figure 1: ISODATA classification

The misclassifications are illustrated by a confusion matrix in Table 2 which indicates that 4 ground truth samples belonging to mining class on the reference data were classified as built-up and 3 out of 4 tarred roads ground truth samples were classified as water bodies. This indicates that spectral properties of mining were relatively similar to the built-up class, whilst tarred roads were similar to water bodies; therefore ISODATA was unable to discriminate subtle differences in their spectral reflectance. Perhaps, a similar explanation can be given for great misclassification in other classes, which indicated a producer's accuracy of less than 60%. Grassland had a producer's

accuracy of 66.7%, whilst water bodies had 100%. On the other hand, all six classes had a user's accuracy of less than 60%, and an overall accuracy was 36.7%. The results indicate that the derived classification using ISODATA classifier were unreliable.

Table 2: Confusion matrix for ISODATA classifier

		Ground Truth								Total	User's
		Bare land	Sparse veg.	Built-up	Mining	Tarred roads	Grassland	Dense veg.	Water bodies		
ISODATA classification	Bare land	62	38	4				3		108	57.4
	Sparse veg.	21	23	2			1	1		48	47.9
	Built-up	9	5	7	4					25	28.0
	Mining				0					0	0.0
	Tarred roads					0				0	0.0
	Grassland	1					4	3		8	50.0
	Dense veg.	27	49	2		1	1	12		92	13.0
	Water bodies	7	6			3		1	2	19	10.5
Total	127	121	15	4	4	6	20	2	300		
Producer's	48.8	19.0	46.7	0.0	0.0	66.7	60.0	100.0		36.7	

$$\widehat{K}=0.16$$

Maximum Likelihood classifier yielded 8 classes identical to those specified in the training of the classification. Figure 3 indicate that ML classifier was able to detect all 8 classes, most of which had a producer's accuracy of more than 60% as shown in Table 3. Large misclassifications occurred in the bare land, mining and dense vegetation classes and had producer's accuracies of 18%, 50% and 30% respectively. Table 3 also indicates that, 88 bare land ground truth samples were misclassified as sparse vegetation and 15 as built-up. For 'mining' class, 2 of 4 ground truth samples were misclassified as bare land and tarred roads respectively, and for dense vegetation, most ground truth samples were misclassified as sparse vegetation bare land, built-up tarred road and grassland. Most of these misclassifications can be explained from Jeffries-Matusita separability analysis in Figure 4, which indicates that about 20% of the class-pairs, namely; bare land and built up, bare land and tarred roads, built-up and tarred roads, and sparse vegetation and bare land; had a relatively low Jeffries-Matusita distance of closer to 1, inferring relatively low inter-class spectral separability, whilst 80% were significantly different, since their distance values were closer to 2. The user's accuracy for 50% of the classes (i.e. 4 out of 8 classes) was above 60% and an overall accuracy of 50.7% was achieved. The results are indicative of a moderate reliability of the derived classification.

Figure 3: Maximum Likelihood classification

Table 3: Confusion matrix for Maximum Likelihood classifier

		Ground Truth								Total	User's
		Bare land	Sparse veg.	Built-up	Mining	Tarred roads	Grassland	Dense veg.	Water bodies		
MLC classification	Bare land	23	9	1	1		1	2		36	63.9
	Sparse veg.	88	102	1				6		198	51.5
	Built-up	15	7	9			1	3		35	25.7
	Mining				1	2				3	66.7
	Tarred roads		3	2	1	4		2		12	33.3
	Grassland	2		1			4	1		8	50.0
	Dense veg.							6		6	100.0
	Water bodies								2	2	100.0
	Total		128	121	15	4	4	6	20	2	300
Producer's		18.0	84.3	60.0	50.0	100.0	66.7	30.0	100.0		50.7

$\hat{K}=0.26$

Figure 4: Jeffries-Matusita class separability

A visual comparison of both ISODATA and ML classifications shows that bare land was overestimated in ISODATA map than in ML map, whilst sparse vegetation was overestimated in ML map than in ISODATA map. Nevertheless, KHAT statistic for both classifiers was found to be less than 0.40, indicating a poor agreement between the ground truth samples and the classifications.

4.2 Object-based classification

The results of the segmentation process at scale level of 30 indicated meaningful objects which represented the shapes of the objects as they occurred in the original image. Figure 5 indicates the results of segmentation process.

Figure 5: Multi resolution segmentation at 30 scale level

An object-based *K*-NN classifier resulted in a visually appealing classification with 8 classes (Figure 6), delineating successfully; tarred roads, mining, dense vegetation along the streams and bare land spaces between sparsely vegetated areas.

Figure 6: Object-based *K*-NN classification

A confusion matrix in Table 4 indicates that 7 out of 8 classes had a producer's accuracy of 70% and above. This is in par with the recommendations made in Foody (2002). Large misclassifications occurred in 'grassland' class, where; 2 out of 6 ground truth samples were classified as bare land and sparse vegetation respectively. The user's accuracies of greater than 80% in most classes indicate that an object-based *K*-NN classification was significantly reliable. Two ground truth samples belonging to sparse vegetation were misclassified as water bodies, resulting in 40% user's accuracy. A KHAT statistic (0.76) for *K*-NN classifier indicated moderate agreement between the classification and ground-truth data. The results are consistent with the findings by Memarian et al. (2012).

Table 4: Confusion matrix for *K*-Nearest Neighbour classifier

		Ground Truth								Totals	User's
		Bare land	Sparse Veg	Built-up	Mining	Tarred roads	Grassland	Dense veg.	Water bodies		
K-NN classification	Bare land	103	13	2	0	0	1	0	0	119	86.6
	Sparse Veg.	22	107	0	0	0	1	3	0	133	80.5
	Built-up	0	0	12	1	0	0	0	0	13	92.3
	Mining	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	3	100.0
	Tarred roads	0	0	0	0	4	0	0	0	4	100.0
	Grassland	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	0	4	100.0
	Dense veg.	1	0	0	0	0	0	11	0	12	91.7
	Water bodies	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	2	5	40.0
Totals		126	121	15	4	4	6	14	2	300	
Producer's		81.7	88.4	80.0	75.0	100.0	66.7	78.6	100.0		82.0

$$\widehat{K} = 0.73$$

5. Conclusions

This study evaluated the performance of different classification techniques in deriving high resolution land cover product from a pan-sharpened SPOT 6 imagery. The results indicated that *K*-NN had the highest overall accuracy of 82% and a KHAT statistic of 0.76, followed by ML classifier with an overall accuracy of 50.7% and a KHAT statistic of 0.26 and finally the ISODATA classifier with an overall accuracy of 36.7% and a KHAT statistic of 0.16. Less agreement between the classification and ground truth data in all 3 methods may have occurred due to differences in dates of SPOT 6 and aerial photographs used for land cover classification and ground truth, respectively. Despite this, an object-based *K*-NN classification was found significant in mapping land cover using SPOT 6 data, and is hereby recommended over conventional pixel-based ISODATA and ML classifiers which were less significant. The results obtained are consistent with results from previous works in related literature. This study establishes that an object-based *K*-NN performed better than the pixel-based ISODATA and ML classifiers when using high resolution data. SPOT 6 data demonstrated that it can be used to produce high resolution land cover product for various applications in South Africa.

Future work will be dedicated to improving the classification accuracy by collecting recent ground truth data. Additionally, a test of significance between classifications to enable statistical comparisons between the derived classifications, as recommended in literature will be conducted.

The advantages offered by object-based classifications were not fully explored in this study; therefore an incorporation of ancillary data such as DEM and NDVI should be explored.

References

- Adams, JB. & Gillespie AR, 2006, *Remote Sensing of landscapes with spectral images-A physical modeling approach*, Cambridge University Press, New York
- Ahmad, A. and Sufahani, SF. 2012, 'Analysis of Landsat 5 TM Data of Malaysian Land
- Al-Ahmadi, FS. & Hames, AS. 2009, 'Comparison of Four Classification Methods to Extract Land Use and Land Cover from Raw Satellite Images for Some Remote Arid Areas, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia' *JKAU; Earth Sci.*, Vol. 20, No.1, pp: 167-191.
- Alparone, L., Wald, L., Chanussot, J., Thomas, C., Gamba, P. and Bruce, LM. 2007, 'Comparison of Pansharpening Algorithms: Outcome of the 2006 GRS-S Data-Fusion Contest' *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, Vol. 45, No. 10, pp. 3012-3021.
- Barbosa, IS. & Maillard, P. 2010, 'Mapping a wetland complex in the Brazilian savannah using an Ikonos image: assessing the potential of a new region-based classifier' *Can. J. Remote Sensing*, vol. 36, Suppl. 2, pp. S231-S242.
- Blaschke, T. 2010, 'Object based image analysis for remote sensing' *ISPRS Journal of Photogrammetry and Remote Sensing*, 65, pp. 2-16.
- Budreski, KA., Wynne, RH., Browder, JO. and Campbell, JB. 2007, 'Comparison of Segment and Pixel-based Non-parametric Land Cover Classification in the Brazilian Amazon Using Multitemporal Landsat TM/ETM+ Imagery' *Photogrammetric Engineering & Remote Sensing*, vol. 73, no. 7, July 2007, pp. 813-827.
- Cambell, JB. and Wynne, RH. 2011, *Introduction to Remote Sensing-Accuracy Assessment*, 5th Edition, The Guilford Press, New York/London
- Clevers, JGPW., Bartholomeus, HM., Mùcher, CA. and de Wit, AJW. 2005, 'Land cover classification with the Medium Resolution Imaging Spectrometer (MERIS)' *New Strategies for European Remote Sensing*, Oluic (ed.), Millpress, Rotterdam, ISBN 90 5966 003 X, pp. 687-694.
- Covers Using ISODATA Clustering Technique' *IEEE Asia-Pacific Conference on Applied Electromagnetics (APACE 2012)*, December 11 - 13, 2012, Melaka, Malaysia
- Elewa, HH., Qaddah, AA. & El-Feel, AA, 2012, 'Determining Potential Sites for Runoff Water Harvesting using Remote Sensing and Geographic Information Systems-Based Modeling in Sinai' *American Journal of Environmental Sciences*, vol. 8, no. 1, pp. 42-55.
- Foody, GM. 2002, 'Status of land cover classification accuracy assessment' *Remote Sensing of Environment*, vol. 80, pp. 185-201.
- Hu, Q., Wu, W., Xia T., Yu, Q., Yang, P., Li, Z. & Song, Q. 2013, 'Exploring the Use of Google Earth Imagery and Object-Based Methods in Land Use/Cover Mapping' *Remote Sens.* vol. 5, pp. 6026-6042, <doi:10.3390/rs5116026>
- Kim, M. & Daigle JJ. 2011, 'Detecting vegetation cover change on the summit of Cadillac Mountain using multi-temporal remote sensing datasets: 1979, 2001, and 2008' *Environmental Monitoring and Assessment*, 180, pp. 63-75.
- Kusimi, JM. 2008, 'Assessing land use and land cover change in the Wassa West District of Ghana using remote sensing' *GeoJournal*, vol. 71, pp. 249-259.
- Loveland, TR., Reed, BC., Brown, JF., Ohlen, DO., Zhu, Z., Yang, L. & Merchant, JW. 2000, 'Development of a global land cover characteristics database and IGBP DISCover from 1 km AVHRR data', *International Journal of Remote Sensing*, vol. 21, no. 6-7, pp. 1303-1330.
- Lück, W., Mhangara, P., Kleyn, L. and Remas, H. 2010, 'Land Cover Field Guide' Prepared for: Chief

Directorate: National Geospatial Information, Pretoria, South Africa

- Matinfar, HR, Sarmadian, F, Alavi Panah, SK & Heck, RJ. 2007, 'Comparisons of Object-Oriented and Pixel-Based Classification of Land Use/Land Cover Types Based on Landsat7, Etm+ Spectral Bands (Case Study: Arid Region of Iran)' *American-Eurasian J. Agric. & Environ. Sci.*, vol. 2, no. 4, pp. 448-456
- Memarian, H., Balasundram, SK. & Khosla, R. 2013, 'Comparison between pixel- and object-based image classification of a tropical landscape using Système Pour l'Observation de la Terre-5 imagery' *International Journal of Applied Remote Sensing*, vol. 7, pp. 073512-1-073512-13, <DOI: 10.1117/1.JRS.7.073512>
- Odindi, J, Mhangara, P, Kakembo, V. 2012, 'Remote sensing land-cover change in Port Elizabeth during South Africa's democratic transition'. *South African Journal of Science*; vol. 108, no. 5/6, Art. #886, pp. 1-7, <<http://dx.doi.org/10.4102/sajs.v108i5/6.886>>
- Oruc, M., Marangoz, AM., & Buyuksalih, G., 2004, 'Comparison of pixel-based and object-oriented classification approaches using Landsat-7 ETM spectral bands'. *Proceedings of ISPRS Conference*, 19-23 July, Istanbul.
- Persello, C & Bruzzone, L. 2012, 'Active Learning for Domain Adaptation in the Supervised Classification of Remote Sensing Images' *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, vol. 50, no. 11, pp.
- Prenzel, B. 2004, 'Remote Sensing-based quantification of land-cover and land-use changes for planning' *Progress in planning*, vol. 61, pp. 281-299.
- Turker, CJ., Townshend, JRG. & Goff, TE. 1985, 'African Land-Cover Classification Using Satellite Data' *Science*, vol. 227, no. 4685, pp. 369-375.
- Wessels, KJ., De Fries, RS., Dempewolf, J., Anderson, LO., Hansen, AJ., Powell, SL. and Moran, EF. 2004, 'Mapping regional land cover with MODIS data for biological conservation: Examples from the Greater Yellowstone Ecosystem, USA and Para' State, Brazil', *Remote Sensing of Environment*, vol. 92, pp. 67-83.
- Whiteside T. and Ahmad W. 2005, 'A comparison of object-oriented and pixel-based classification methods for mapping land cover in northern Australia.' *Proceedings of SSC2005 Spatial intelligence, innovation and praxis: The national biennial Conference of the Spatial Sciences Institute*, September 2005. Melbourne: Spatial Sciences Institute. ISBN 09581366-2-9
- Yuan, F., Sawaya, KE., Loeffelholz, BC. & Bauer, ME. 2005, 'Land cover classification and image analysis of the Twin Cities (Minnesota) Metropolitan area by multitemporal landsat remote sensing.' *Remote Sensing of Environment*, vol. 98, pp. 317 - 328.